

1 **Future CH₄ as modelled by a fully coupled Earth system model: Prescribed GHG**
2 **concentrations vs. interactive CH₄ sources and sinks**

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 We have used the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) Earth system model
20 GISS-E2.1 to study the future budgets and trends of global and regional CH₄ under different
21 emission scenarios, using both the prescribed GHG concentrations as well as the interactive
22 CH₄ sources and sinks setup of the model, to quantify the model performance and its
23 sensitivity to CH₄ sources and sinks. We have used the Current Legislation (CLE) and the
24 Maximum Feasible Reduction (MFR) emission scenarios from the ECLIPSE V6b emission
25 database to simulate the future evolution of CH₄ sources, sinks, and levels from 2015 to 2050.

26

27 Results show that the prescribed GHG version underestimates the observed surface CH₄
28 concentrations during the period between 1995 and 2023 by 1%, with the largest
29 underestimations over the continental emission regions, while the interactive simulation
30 underestimates the observations by 2%, with the biases largest over oceans and smaller over
31 the continents. For the future, the MFR scenario simulates lower global surface CH₄
32 concentrations and burdens compared to the CLE scenario, however in both cases, global
33 surface CH₄ and burden continue to increase through 2050 compared to present day. In
34 addition, the interactive simulation calculates slightly larger O₃ and OH mixing ratios, in

35 particular over the northern hemisphere, leading to slightly decreased CH₄ lifetime in the
36 present day. The CH₄ forcing is projected to increase in both scenarios, in particular in the
37 CLE scenario, from 0.53 W m⁻² in the present day to 0.73 W m⁻² in 2050. In addition, the
38 interactive simulations estimate slightly higher tropospheric O₃ forcing compared to
39 prescribed simulations, due to slightly higher O₃ mixing ratios simulated by the interactive
40 models. While in the CLE, tropospheric O₃ forcing continues to increase, the MFR scenario
41 leads to a decrease in tropospheric O₃ forcing, leading to a climate benefit. Our results
42 highlight that in the interactive models, the response of concentrations are not necessarily
43 linear with the changes in emissions as the chemistry is non-linear, and dependent on the
44 oxidative capacity of the atmosphere. Therefore, it is important to have the CH₄ sources and
45 chemical sinks to be represented comprehensively in climate models.

46

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Atmospheric methane (CH₄) is the second most important anthropogenic greenhouse gas with
49 a global warming potential 27–30 times that of carbon dioxide (CO₂) over a 100-year time
50 horizon (Forster et al., 2021). CH₄ emissions mix through the troposphere on timescales
51 shorter than the globally averaged atmospheric lifetime (AMAP, 2015b), thus the average
52 trend in atmospheric concentration is roughly the same everywhere on Earth. While global
53 concentrations have increased at varying rates, the mechanisms behind these variations are
54 still not fully understood. Between approximately 2000–2005 there was no growth in global
55 CH₄ mixing ratios but from about 2007, the growth increased and then accelerated from 2015
56 (Nisbet et al., 2019) till today. CH₄ is emitted into the atmosphere from both anthropogenic
57 activities (e.g., agriculture, energy, industry, transportation, waste management, and biomass
58 burning) and natural processes (e.g., wetlands, termites, permafrost thawing and oceanic and
59 geological processes), and it is removed from the atmosphere mainly by reaction with
60 hydroxyl radical (OH) in the troposphere. The uncertainty in the chemical loss of CH₄ by OH
61 is estimated around 15 % (Saunio et al., 2016). Depending on the approach used, total CH₄
62 emissions from natural and anthropogenic sources range between 575 and 669 Tg yr⁻¹
63 (Saunio et al., 2024) and furthermore, top-down versus bottom-up estimates of CH₄ sources
64 and sinks do not match, underscoring the incomplete knowledge of global CH₄ dynamics
65 (Stavert et al., 2022). Understanding and quantifying the global CH₄ budget is important for
66 assessing realistic pathways to mitigate climate change. Recently, AMAP (2021) and von
67 Salzen et al. (2022) showed that ambitious global reductions of CH₄, together with black
68 carbon, could lead to Arctic climate benefits by 2050, similar to those from global CO₂

69 reductions in a climate-focused mitigation strategy. A better understanding of the drivers of
70 trends and variability in CH₄ abundance over the recent past is therefore critical for building
71 confidence in projections of future CH₄ levels. In addition, a better understanding of CH₄
72 sinks is needed to better understand the potential to enhance the natural sinks for atmospheric
73 CH₄ removal, and determine removal scales required (NASEM, 2024).

74

75 To date, important natural sources such as oceanic CH₄ (Weber et al., 2019; Davies et al.,
76 2023), lakes (Zhuang et al., 2023), and permafrost thawing (Turetsky et al., 2020), and sinks
77 such as tropospheric halogens (e.g. Basu et al., 2022), and some VOCs such as isoprene
78 (Guenther et al., 2006; Arnold et al., 2010) impact the atmospheric oxidative capacity, are
79 either missing or outdated in the climate models participating in the recent IPCC (Forster et
80 al., 2021) and AMAP (AMAP, 2021) assessments. For example, halogens influence the
81 atmosphere's oxidative capacity by affecting the abundant hydroxyl radicals (OH) and
82 thereby interfering with the CH₄ sink. A significant atmospheric CH₄ sink is direct removal
83 via chlorine (Cl) reactions (Basu et al., 2022), and the indirect influence on OH via the
84 catalytic destruction of O₃ by bromine (Br) and iodine (I). These processes are not accounted
85 for in majority of the ESMs. Halogens can decrease tropospheric O₃ by 11–15% and OH by
86 8% [9,10] and increase global CH₄ lifetime and radiative forcing (Li et al., 2022).

87

88 To date, Earth system models (ESM), in most cases, have specified atmospheric CH₄
89 concentration to follow prescribed pathways, thereby disallowing important coupling
90 mechanisms, such as coupling between global wetlands and atmospheric chemistry. For
91 example, in all models contributing to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
92 (CMIP6: Eyring et al., 2016), global mean CH₄ concentrations were prescribed at the surface,
93 except for some future simulations with GISS-E2-1-G, the NASA Goddard Institute for
94 Space Studies (GISS) chemistry–climate model version E2.1 (Kelley et al., 2020), which
95 used interactive online CH₄ emissions. Recently, Folberth et al. (2022) implemented the
96 interactive CH₄ chemistry in the UK-ESM1 ESM, where they have found a large negative
97 bias between the 1920s and present-day global anthropogenic CH₄. They proposed that this
98 underestimation could be either a model bias in simulated processes (sinks) or an
99 underestimate of historical emissions, therefore recommending better estimates and
100 reconstructions of past CH₄ emissions. In addition, the emissions-driven interactive chemistry
101 setup of the EMAC chemistry-climate model has been used by Stecher et al. (2024) to
102 perform idealized perturbation simulations driven either by increased carbon dioxide (CO₂)

103 mixing ratios, or by increased CH₄ emission fluxes. The CH₄ emission flux perturbation leads
104 to a large increase of CH₄ mixing ratios due to increased atmospheric CH₄ lifetime. It is
105 though important to account for sources and sinks of CH₄ when assessing its impacts and
106 future evolution (Shindell et al., 2024).

107

108 The aim of this study is to evaluate the performance of the GISS-E2.1 ESM in simulating
109 observed atmospheric CH₄ concentrations in the near past using its interactive CH₄
110 chemistry, compare with the prescribed GHG simulations, and predict the future CH₄
111 concentrations under two emission scenarios in the frame of the AMAP SLCF activities.

112

113 **2. Material and Methods**

114 2.1. GISS-E2.1 Earth system model

115 GISS-E2.1 is the CMIP6 version of the GISS modelE Earth system model (Kelly et al., 2020;
116 Miller et al., 2020). GISS-E2.1 has a horizontal resolution of 2° in latitude by 2.5° in
117 longitude and 40 vertical layers extending from the surface to 0.1 hPa in the lower
118 mesosphere. The tropospheric chemistry scheme used in GISS-E2.1 (Shindell et al., 2013)
119 includes inorganic chemistry of O_x, NO_x, HO_x, CO, and organic chemistry of CH₄ and
120 higher hydrocarbons using the CBM-IV scheme (Gery et al., 1989), and the stratospheric
121 chemistry scheme (Shindell et al., 2013), which includes chlorine and bromine chemistry
122 together with polar stratospheric clouds. CH₄ is primarily oxidized by the hydroxyl radical
123 (OH), which is sensitive to NO_x, CO, and VOC levels.

124

125 2.2. Emissions

126 2.2.1. Anthropogenic emissions

127 In this study, we used the ECLIPSE V6b (Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2020) emissions, which
128 has been developed with support of the EU-funded Action on Black Carbon in the Arctic
129 (EUA-BCA) and used in the framework of the recent AMAP Assessment on Short Lived
130 Climate Forcers (AMAP, 2021, von Salzen et al., 2022). The ECLIPSE V6b emissions
131 dataset is a further evolution of the scenarios established in the EU funded ECLIPSE project
132 (Stohl et al., 2015; Klimont et al., 2017). ECLIPSE V6b has a 0.5°x0.5° spatial resolution,
133 and includes nine sectors: energy, industry, solvent use, transport, residential combustion,
134 agriculture, open burning of agricultural waste, waste treatment, gas flaring and venting, and
135 international shipping. A monthly pattern for each gridded layer was provided at a 0.5°x0.5°
136 grid level. The ECLIPSE V6b dataset, used in this study, includes an estimate for 1990 to

137 2015 using statistical data and two scenarios extending to 2050 that rely on the same energy
138 projections from the World Energy Outlook 2018 (IEA, 2018) but have different assumptions
139 about the implementation of air pollution reduction technologies, as described below.

140

141 The future anthropogenic emissions (2015-2050) are defined in two scenarios. The Current
142 Legislation (CLE) scenario assumes efficient implementation of the current air pollution
143 legislation enacted before 2018, while the Maximum Feasible Reduction (MFR) scenario
144 assumes implementation of best available emission reduction technologies. The assumptions
145 and the details for the CLE and MFR scenarios (as well as other scenarios developed within
146 the ECLIPSE V6b family) can be found in Höglund-Isaksson et al. (2020).

147

148 2.2.2. Natural emissions

149 The natural emissions of sea salt, biogenic VOCs, dimethylsulfide (DMS), and dust are
150 calculated interactively. CH₄ emissions from wetlands in GISS-E2.1 are calculated online
151 using the model's climate (Shindell et al., 2003, 2004). The emissions module calculates the
152 response to GISS-E2.1 upper layer soil temperature and precipitation anomalies (Shindell et
153 al., 2004). The model uses the wetland locations from Fung et al. (1991), which are then
154 modified by the emissions model described above. Locations determined to contain wetlands
155 which were not in the dataset were given the latitudinal mean emission value. In addition, the
156 wetland emissions have been tuned by a tuning factor calculated to get a similar burden and
157 lifetime as in the prescribed simulations during the historical period (1995-2023) in order to
158 better follow the global observations. This tuning approach does not take into account the
159 changes in changes in OH or regional differences in CH₄ emissions and concentrations but
160 improves the model performance by getting closer to the observed global CH₄ concentrations.
161 The calculated wetland tuning factor for the 1995-2014 period is then applied also in the
162 future period 2015-2050.

163

164 The prescribed simulations are based on the global CH₄ mixing ratios provided by Olivié et
165 al. (2021), which have been calculated using a simple box-model for the different scenarios
166 that uses as input timeseries of global- and annual-mean emissions of CH₄, NO_x, CO and
167 VOCs and of global-mean temperature, and calculates global- and annual-mean
168 concentrations of CH₄. The box model (Olivié et al., 2021) starts in 2015 from observed CH₄
169 concentrations, leading to a good agreement of the modelled CH₄ concentrations with
170 observations. The background CH₄ emissions over the period 1990-2015 have been estimated

171 by an iterative method, where the background time-varying CH₄ emission were calculated
 172 that best reproduce the observed CH₄ concentrations, which leads to a good agreement with
 173 the historical prescribed simulation and the observations The average background emissions
 174 over the period 2005-2014 are then used as initial conditions for 2015 and onwards. The
 175 emissions used in the box model, along with the calculated global CH₄ concentrations and
 176 lifetime are presented in Figure 1. As seen in Figure 1a, the global CH₄ emissions continue to
 177 grow in the CLE scenario from 592 Tg in 2020 to 688 Tg in 2050, while in MFR, the
 178 emissions drop significantly from 592 Tg in 2020 to 496 Tg in 2025, then continues to
 179 decrease but slightly down to 480 Tg in 2050. The lifetime slightly increases from 9.22 years
 180 to 9.26 year in CLE (Figure 1b) as the emissions continue to increase in CLE. On the other
 181 hand, in MFR, due to strong reductions in CO, NO_x and VOC, the net effect is an increase in
 182 the lifetime until 2025 to 9.2 years, and then a slight decrease to 8.8 years in 2050. This lead
 183 to a continue increase in global CH₄ concentrations (Figure 1c) in CLE from 1874 ppb to
 184 2194 ppb in 2050. In MFR, CH₄ concentrations decrease to 1569 ppb in 2050.

185

186

187 Figure 1. Olivié et al. (2021) box model global CH₄ a) emissions, b) lifetime, and c)
 188 concentrations under CLE and MFR scenarios.

189

190 The tuning procedure assumes that the anthropogenic and other natural CH₄ emissions are
 191 correct and that the large difference in CH₄ burdens in the prescribed and interactive
 192 simulations are attributed to the wetland emissions, which are very uncertain and contribute
 193 largest among the natural emissions (Sauonois et al. 2024). Other natural methane sources are
 194 fixed at values of 20 Tg yr⁻¹ for termites, close to the 25 Tg yr⁻¹ from Basu et al. (2022), and
 195 27 Tg yr⁻¹ for combined geological + ocean + lake sources (Fung et al., 1991). There are no
 196 changes in methane emissions due to thawing permafrost (Turetsky et al., 2020) or increased
 197 release from hydrates over time. These emissions are also likely on the low side compared to
 198 newer literature, where global oceanic CH₄ emissions are estimated to be 6-12 Tg yr⁻¹
 199 (Weber et al., 2019) and lake emissions are estimated to be 24.0 ± 8.4 Tg yr⁻¹ (Zhuang et al.,

200 2023). These suggest that the natural CH₄ emissions in the GISS-E2.1 model should be
201 updated based on recent findings.

202

203 GISS-E2.1 includes only the chemical loss of CH₄ with OH (Shindell et al., 2013) and the
204 soil sink is constant at 30 Tg yr⁻¹ (Fung et al., 1991). Other known direct chemical sinks such
205 as chlorine, or the indirect sink due to other halogens affecting OH are not included in the
206 model.

207

208 2.2.3. Simulations

209

210 Both the prescribed and interactive simulations are AMIP-type simulations, with prescribed
211 SSTs and sea-ice concentrations calculated by the fully coupled GISS-E2.1 contribution to
212 the AMAP (2021) assessment, described in detail in Im et al. (2021) and von Salzen et al.
213 (2022). The prescribed simulation used methane mixing ratios calculated by Olivié et al.
214 (2021). We carried out two sets of simulations that used the CLE and MFR emission
215 scenarios. Each simulation in these two sets of scenarios were initialized from a set of fully
216 coupled recent past simulations (1990-2014) to ensure a smooth continuation from recent past
217 to future.

218

219 3. Results and Discussions

220 3.1. Anthropogenic and natural methane emissions

221 The anthropogenic and natural CH₄ emissions in the present day (averaged over 2015-2020)
222 and their spatial distribution are presented in Figure 2 and 3, respectively, while their
223 temporal evolution in the historical (1995-2014) and future (2015-2050) are presented in
224 Figures 3 and 6, respectively. The natural emissions (380±8 Tg yr⁻¹) in the present day are
225 simulated to be larger than the anthropogenic emissions (285±3 Tg yr⁻¹), leading to a total
226 CH₄ emission of 650±10 Tg yr⁻¹ in agreement with Saunio et al. (2024). Both anthropogenic
227 and natural emissions increase in the historical period, going from 222 and 265 Tg,
228 respectively, to 278 and 321 Tg in 2015, respectively, with the total global CH₄ emission of
229 645 Tg (Figure 3). In the present day, wetland CH₄ emissions are estimated to be 332±8 Tg
230 yr⁻¹, which is much larger than the estimate of 155-217 Tg yr⁻¹ in Saunio et al. (2020). On
231 the other hand, the global anthropogenic CH₄ emission we in the present study (285 Tg yr⁻¹)
232 is smaller than 369 Tg yr⁻¹ in Saunio et al. (2024).

233

234 Anthropogenic CH₄ emissions are largest in south and east Asia, while sources over Europe,
 235 North and South America, and sub-Saharan Africa stand out (Figure 3). Wetland emissions
 236 are largest in south America and sub-Saharan Africa, as well as parts of eastern Europe and
 237 Siberia. CH₄ from biomass burning stands out in the fire hotspots over the Amazons and
 238 Africa. CH₄ from termites are primarily over the southern hemisphere. Overall, CH₄
 239 emissions are largest over south America, sub-Saharan Africa, and south and east Asia.

248 Figure 2. a) CH₄ emissions and their sources in the present day (2015-2020 mean), b) the
 249 sources of natural CH₄ emissions, and c) the evolution of CH₄ emissions in the 1995-2014
 250 period (right) as modelled by the interactive simulation. Anthr stands for anthropogenic,
 251 BBurn for biomass burning, and Term for termites. Soil stands for the soil sink for CH₄.
 252

253
 254 Figure 3. Global distribution of anthropogenic, wetland + tundra, biomass burning, termite,
 255 and other CH₄ sources averaged over 2015-2020.

256

257 3.1. Model evaluation

258 The global atmospheric CH₄ mixing ratios (ppm) as simulated by the prescribed and
 259 interactive simulations are evaluated against those observed by NOAA (Lan et al., 2024)

260 between 1995 and 2014 (Figure 4). The interactive simulation underestimates the observed
 261 global levels by 5% (Mean bias (MB) = -0.09 ppm), while the prescribed simulation
 262 underestimates by 2% (MB = -0.04 ppm). The observed temporal evolution is well-captured by
 263 the prescribed simulation (r = 0.99), while the interactive simulation has a much lower
 264 correlation (r = 0.65). This is expected as the box-model that calculated CH_4 concentrations
 265 used in the prescribed simulations was tuned via the natural emissions over the period 1990-
 266 2014 to correspond as good as possible the observations CH_4 concentration. The deviation
 267 between the prescribed and interactive simulations after 2007 is due to a larger increase in
 268 chemical sink compared to the sources after 2007, leading to a decrease in mixing ratios.
 269
 270

271
 272 Figure 4. Observed and simulated global mean CH_4 concentrations in 1995-2014 period.

273
 274 We have also evaluated the surface CH_4 concentrations by the two simulations against
 275 observations at various stations under Global Atmospheric Watch (GAW), as shown in
 276 Figure 5. The prescribed simulation underestimates the GAW surface CH_4 observations
 277 during the period between 1995 and 2023 by 1% [-8.4% 2.0%]. The largest underestimations
 278 are over the continental emission regions such as North America, Europe, and Asia, while
 279 biases are smallest over oceans. On the other hand, the simulation with interactive sources
 280 and sinks underestimates the GAW observations more than the prescribed simulation, by
 281 2.3% [-8.4% 5.9%]. Opposite to the prescribed simulation, the biases are positive over oceans
 282 and more negative over the continents. The interactive simulation, with large sources

283 exclusively over land and strong sink over oceans, has a land/ocean ratio larger than 1 while
284 the prescribed simulation has this ratio equal to 1 as it distributes the global prescribed CH₄
285 concentration equally in longitude over a given latitude (Figure 8). This clearly shows that
286 using interactive sources and sinks has large impacts on relative surface values across
287 geographies, so that there's a potential to constrain sources and sinks' distributions using
288 observations. This also implies that the sink is regionally off due to the missing of some of
289 the other OH-related emissions such as too low CO or too high NO_x over land, or other
290 chemistry mechanisms such as halogens over oceans.

291

292

293 Figure 5. Normalized mean bias (*MNB*) in % in simulated surface CH₄ concentrations from a)
294 prescribed and b) interactive (right panel) simulations in 1995-2014 period.

295

296 3.2. Evolution of future CH₄ sources and sinks

297 As shown in Figure 6, CH₄ emissions continue to rise in the CLE scenario to 757 Tg in 2050,
298 while in MFR, there is a rapid decline to around 600 Tg by 2025, which then stabilizes. The
299 decline in the MFR scenario is due to the large reduction of anthropogenic emissions until
300 2025, which then continues to decrease very slightly, while the wetland emissions stay
301 around 350 ± 10 Tg yr⁻¹ throughout the simulation period. As shown in Figure 6c, the CH₄
302 chemical sinks in the CLE increase throughout the simulation period, while the sink in MFR
303 decreases slightly in the same period, which leads to a slight increase in the simulated CH₄
304 mixing ratios in the interactive simulation as opposed to the prescribed simulation. Under the
305 MFR, less OH is simulated by the model (not shown) compared to the CLE scenario,
306 however in both scenarios, OH continues to increase between 2020 and 2050. This also
307 points to the non-linear chemistry in the model concerning oxidative capacity (e.g. OH) and
308 CH₄, which does not respond linearly to the changes in emissions.

309

310 Figure 6. Evolution of global CH₄ emissions in the interactive a) CLE and b) MFR scenarios,
 311 respectively, and c) CH₄ chemical sink.

312

313 3.3. Evolution of future CH₄ mixing ratios and lifetime

314 The prescribed global mean CH₄ mixing ratios increase in the CLE scenario and decrease in
 315 the MFR scenario (Figure 7). In the interactive simulations, as the future CH₄ emissions
 316 increase in the CLE scenario (Figure 6), the simulated CH₄ mixing ratios also increase,
 317 following nicely the prescribed CH₄ mixing ratios ($r=0.99$, $NMB=-2\%$), reaching to ~2.2 ppm
 318 by 2050. The simulated lifetimes are also similar in the prescribed and interactive simulations
 319 in the present day (~8.4 years). The lifetimes slightly increase towards 2050 to ~8.6 years in
 320 all simulations, except for the interactive MFR simulation, where the lifetime increases to 9.2
 321 years, and cannot capture the decrease in the prescribed global mixing ratios.

322

323

324 Figure 7. a) Evolution of simulated and observed (NOAA) global CH₄ concentrations and b)
 325 lifetime in the prescribed and interactive simulations.

326

327 As expected, the interactive MFR scenario simulates lower global surface CH₄ concentrations
 328 and burdens compared to the interactive CLE scenario, however in both cases, global surface
 329 CH₄ and burden continue to increase through 2050 compared to present day. Both the
 330 interactive CLE and MFR scenarios show increased concentrations over the whole globe
 331 (Figure 8). In the CLE scenario, CH₄ concentrations increase largest over the northern
 332 hemisphere, in particular over India and East China, and the Pacific. On the other hand, the

333 MFR scenario shows increases particularly over the whole Southern Hemisphere, however
334 much smaller compared to CLE.

335

336 While the evolution of global CH₄ concentrations in the future as simulated by the interactive
337 model is consistent with the prescribed simulations under CLE scenario, as shown in Figure
338 7a, the interactive model under the MFR scenario simulates an increasing global CH₄
339 concentration opposite to the prescribed MFR simulation that show a decreasing trend. This
340 is due to the different complexity of the chemistry mechanisms in the box model and GISS-
341 E2.1, that results in different lifetimes; CH₄ lifetime decreases in MFR in the box model
342 (Figure 1b) while it increases in GISS-E2.1 (Figure 7b). This highlights that the response of
343 concentrations are not necessarily linear with the changes in emissions as the chemistry is
344 non-linear, and dependent on the oxidative capacity of the atmosphere due to other species
345 such as CO and VOCs. In addition, there are also differences in the CH₄ sinks; chlorine sink
346 is taken into account in the box model while it is not in the GISS-E2.1, leading to less
347 chemical removal and longer lifetime compared to the box model. Finally, the simple box
348 model is based on global and annual mean emissions, which does not take into account the
349 spatial and temporal (i.e. seasonal variation) in emissions and chemistry that is implemented
350 in GISS-E2.1. These difference lead to difference responses in CH₄ lifetime and therefore
351 concentrations in the box model and GISS-E2.1, even if the emissions are similar.

352

353

354 Figure 8. Spatial distribution of a) CH₄ concentrations in 2020 as simulated by the prescribed
355 and b) interactive simulations and the difference in 2050-2020 CH₄ concentrations as
356 simulated by the c) interactive CLE and d) MFR scenarios.

357

358 3.4. Tropospheric chemistry impacts

359 We have investigated the difference between the surface ozone (O₃) concentrations in the
360 prescribed and interactive simulations both in its geographical distribution in year 2020 and
361 evolution over time in the CLE and MFR scenarios (Figure 9). The geographical distribution
362 of surface O₃ in the two simulations are very similar (Figure 9a,b) with highest levels over
363 south and east Asia, as well as eastern U.S. and Eastern Mediterranean, and lowest
364 concentrations over the Pacific and South America. The differences between the two
365 simulations (Figure 8c) are largest over southern hemisphere, with the interactive simulation
366 giving larger O₃ concentrations over the ocean by up to 4 ppbs and over south Africa by up to
367 7 ppbs.

368

369 Similar to surface O₃, we have also calculated the hydroxyl radical (OH) surface mixing ratio
370 in the two simulations (Figure 10a, b). The patterns are very similar in the two simulations,
371 with the interactive simulation calculating slightly higher concentrations globally compared
372 to the prescribed simulation, by up to 0.06 ppt (45%), particularly over the Eastern
373 Mediterranean and the Arabian Peninsula, as well as over the oceans (Figure 10c).

374

375

376 Figure 9. Geographical distribution of 2020 surface O₃ in the a) prescribed, and b) interactive

377 simulations, c) their difference, and d) temporal evolution of global surface O₃ concentrations
378 in the interactive CLE and MFR scenarios.

392 Figure 10. Geographical distribution of 2020 surface OH in the a) prescribed, and b)
393 interactive simulations, and c) their difference.

394

395 3.5. Climate impacts

396 We calculated the top of the atmosphere (TOA) instantaneous net (shortwave + longwave)
397 radiative forcing due to CH₄ (RF_{CH₄}) in the CLE and MFR scenarios, using the formulation
398 from Etminan et al. (2016). As seen in Figure 11a, the global mean TOA RF_{CH₄} increases
399 from 0.42 W m⁻² in 2020 to 0.56 W m⁻² in 2050 in the CLE scenario, while in the MFR,
400 RF_{CH₄} slightly increase to 0.46 W m⁻² in 2050 compared to 2020. In the present day (2020),
401 the 0.53 W m⁻² RF_{CH₄} is in agreement with the previous estimates (e.g. Shindell et al., 2013;
402 Bellouin et al., 2020; IPCC, 2021), and is largest over the equatorial regions and the oceans,
403 up to more 0.6 W m⁻² (Figure 11b). Both in CLE and MFR scenarios, direct RF_{CH₄} increases
404 geographically up to 0.71 W m⁻² and 0.58 W m⁻², respectively, and the changes in 2050-2020
405 RF_{CH₄} are mostly over the same regions as in the present day, and slightly decreases over the
406 polar regions (Figure 11c,d). The global CH₄ forcing in both prescribed and interactive
407 simulations follow the global CH₄ concentrations (Figure 7a)

408

409

410 Figure 11. a) Temporal evolution of global RF_{CH_4} ($W\ m^{-2}$) in the interactive CLE and MFR
 411 scenarios, b) geographical distribution of in RF_{CH_4} 2020, c) difference between 2050 and
 412 2020 RF_{CH_4} in CLE, and d) difference between 2050 and 2020 RF_{CH_4} in MFR.

413

414 In addition to CH_4 , we have also calculated direct radiative forcing of tropospheric O_3
 415 (RF_{TropO_3}) in the present day and future compared to the preindustrial period (1850), using a
 416 two call to the radiation scheme, in order to quantify the impact on prescribed vs interactive
 417 CH_4 on RF_{TropO_3} . Figure 12 shows the global RF_{TropO_3} in the prescribed and interactive
 418 simulations under the CLE and MFR scenarios. The prescribed and interactive simulations
 419 estimate similar RF_{TropO_3} of around $0.30-0.35\ W\ m^{-2}$ in 2020, consistent with previous
 420 estimates (Shindell et al., 2003, 2013a,b) . Under the CLE scenario, RF_{TropO_3} slightly
 421 increases to $0.37\ W\ m^{-2}$ in 2050 in both prescribed and interactive simulations. Under the
 422 MFR scenario, RF_{TropO_3} decreases to around $0.15-0.20\ W\ m^{-2}$ in 2050. Overall, the interactive
 423 simulations estimate slightly higher RF_{TropO_3} compared to prescribed simulations, due to
 424 slightly higher O_3 mixing ratios simulated by the interactive models.

425

426 Figure 12. Global tropospheric O₃ radiative forcing in 2015-2050 as simulated by the
 427 prescribed and interactive simulations under CLE and MFR scenarios.

428

429 **Conclusions**

430 We simulated the future atmospheric CH₄ levels and its impacts on tropospheric chemistry
 431 and climate under two emission scenarios for the 1995-2050 period, using the GISS-E2.1
 432 ESM with AMIP-type prescribed GHG as well as interactive CH₄ sources and sinks.

433

434 While the prescribed GHG version underestimates the observed surface CH₄ concentrations
 435 during the period between 1995 and 2023 by 1%, the interactive simulation underestimates
 436 the observations slightly more than the prescribed simulation (by 2%), with the biases largest
 437 over oceans and smaller over the continents, opposite to the prescribed simulation. This
 438 geographical difference is attributed to the fact that the prescribed simulation distributes the
 439 global prescribed CH₄ concentration equally in longitude over a given latitude, while the
 440 interactive version uses a realistic geographical distribution of emissions. The interactive
 441 simulation moderately captures the observed historical CH₄ surface concentrations ($r = \sim 0.5$),
 442 which shows an increase from 1995 to present day. In the future, the MFR scenario simulates

443 lower global CH₄ levels compared to the CLE scenario, however in both cases, global CH₄
444 continues to increase. The increase in CH₄ levels under CLE is consistent with the increasing
445 anthropogenic and natural emissions, while under MFR, even though the anthropogenic
446 emissions increase, CH₄ lifetime and concentrations continue to increase slightly due the non-
447 linear chemistry and feedbacks in the model. . In addition, the interactive simulation
448 calculates slightly larger O₃ and OH mixing ratios, in particular over the northern
449 hemisphere. Finally, the direct radiative forcing due to CH₄ is projected to increase in both
450 scenarios from 0.42 W m⁻² in the present day to 0.73 W m⁻² and 0.46 W m⁻² in 2050 in CLE
451 and MFR, respectively.

452

453 Our results highlight that in the interactive models, the response of concentrations are not
454 necessarily linear with the changes in emissions as the chemistry is non-linear, and dependent
455 on the oxidative capacity of the atmosphere also due to other species that impact OH. This
456 implies that models should be improved regarding the chemical composition and processes
457 that influence chemical sinks of CH₄, such as halogens, which both directly removes CH₄, or
458 indirectly by decreasing OH and therefore increasing CH₄ lifetime, as well as CH₄ emissions
459 from natural sources such as oceanic, lake, and thawing permafrost emissions, in order to
460 realistically simulate the chemical composition and the oxidative capacity of the atmosphere
461 and its impacts on climate. Therefore, CH₄ levels and lifetime as simulated by different
462 interactive climate models are very sensitive to differences in the sources, sinks, and the
463 complexity in chemistry in these models. Future work should also focus on fully-coupled
464 simulations to quantify the temperature impact of climate impacts of CH₄ in the interactive
465 climate models.

466

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